

Participatory tools

PHOTOLANUGAGE

INTERNAL FUNCTIONING AND BUILDING A COMMUNITY: BUILDING A COMMUNITY

How to help people work together with people they may not already know? How to build team spirit?

Multi-actors projects bring together individuals and organisations with different skills, knowledge and working habits. It is easier to stay in one's comfort zone with actors who work the same way as one does or at least with whom one is used to working. At the beginning of the project, during the creation and the first moments of the consortium's life, you need to plan time to encourage the links between the actors to facilitate collective work.

How to solve it

It is helpful to create team spirit and understanding between actors within the group

You can leave space for expression adapted to each person (e.g., a farmer during a farm visit). To ease the exchanges, you need to break down any fictitious barriers that may exist between the different types of actors (e.g. between farmers and researchers).

Word of advice

It is helpful to plan regular "face to face" meetings, sometimes in an informal setting. You need to take the time to identify and understand potential barriers between partners to address them better.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Photolanugage - A picture is worth a thousand words. Say it with a picture.

Description of the tool

- **What:** to introduce themselves, to present their experience, to share representations, to look for creative solutions
- **How long:** 5 to 15' per participant, depending on the objective
- **How many:** 2 to 20 (The more participants, the longer it takes)
- **What you'll need:** You can use cards that already exist (GIMCA©, Dixit© ...), or you can prepare your own set of pictures (it takes time to gather a good set).

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

Steps:

- Place the cards on a flat surface (e.g. a table) visible and accessible to all
- Clarifies the question you are asking the participants and make sure it is clear to everyone
- Suggest that they each choose one or more card(s) that represent(s) what they want to express
- Each person, in turn, shows their card and explains how they understand it and how it answers the question asked.

Tips

- For the facilitator
 - Provide a clear question
 - To introduce oneself, express a feeling, an opinion (individual expression), it is not a debate
 - Rules of kindness, listening, neutrality/not judging
 - Short answer requested in instructions
 - Synthesis to be built and capitalized
- The logistic
 - Set of various/nice pictures
 - Possible from distance
 - Beware of the time it takes

More tools: [Icebreaker](#) (e.g. bingo, weather of the day, cross-presentation).

